
The Time Is Now

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How I Found Myself in Public Interest Tech

- **Computer Engineering Degree**
- **Software Engineer @ IBM**
- **Strategy @ FBI Science & Technology**
- **Policy @ White House OSTP**
- **Director of Engineering, PIT @ New America**

Technology: It's so Fast!

“Technology is Moving Faster Than Ever Before”

--Business Insider

“Is Tech Moving Too Fast for You to Keep Up With?”

--Wired

“Technology Feels Like It's Accelerating – Because it Is”

--Singularity Hub

Tech + Innovation

in·no·va·tion | \ ,i-nə-'vā-shən \

1 : the introduction of something new

2 : a new idea, method, or device : NOVELTY

Technological Innovation is an extended concept of innovation

Life as a Program Lead in Public Interest Tech

- Managing implementation projects that address social issues
- Fundraising for core costs and operating costs
- Building partnerships with governments, non-profits, communities
- Learning from and teaching others in the public interest tech space

Common Struggles

Mission-driven often means
wanting greater impact

What do we mean by innovation?

What we work on
versus
How we do the work

Progress and sustained impact require focus

- Diversity and inclusion
- Working models
- Funding the work

Diversity and inclusion

- Tech industry overall lacks diversity
- Difference between
 - Designing for and designing with
 - Including and inclusion
- The stories we tell

Working Models

- Fellowships, fellowships, fellowships
- Consolidating, analyzing, and presenting data
- Long-lasting community partnerships
- Business ventures

Funding the Work

- Philanthropic dollars
- Academic grants
- Fiscal sponsors
- Social enterprises

What Will You Do?

- Diversity and Inclusion
- Working Models
- Funding the work

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